

UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON

Assessing the realism of VISSIM's cyclist model in the UK context

Supervisor: Ioannis Kaparias, Shahjahan Miah

Alejandro González de la Fuente

Student Number: 30445086

MSc in Transportation Planning and Engineering

Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences

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Declaration of Authorship

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Abstract

Cycling is a sustainable mode of transport that offers several social, environmental and economic benefits to society. However, in the UK, cycle trips represent only 2% of all journeys completed. The cycling and walking investment strategy is one measure amongst several that the government has been taken to decrease congestion. Greater cycling infrastructure has been proposed, aiming to deliver safer, better integrated and more attractive routes for bicycle users. For this to be achieved, detailed planning is required, it is necessary to model different scenarios to prevent possible safety problems as well as simply visualising the best option.

VISSIM, a traffic simulation software, calibrated its cyclist model using data from Copenhagen. The aim of this project is, therefore, to investigate the realism of the VISSIM cyclist model in the UK context. First, trajectory data was collected via a field experiment with real cyclists riding an instrumented bicycle at selected sites around the University of Southampton in semi-controlled condition scenarios. Then, a simulation of the corresponding scenarios in VISSIM software was created. Finally, a comparison was made between the real and simulated trajectories to assess the realism of the latter.

Results showed that VISSIM software can successfully simulate almost any cycling scenario. However, some limitations were found and should be considered when planning cycling network additions or modifications. For instance, the speed and acceleration distributions outcomes differed from the ones in Copenhagen. Nevertheless, these parameters can be introduced manually to the software. Thus, this calibration can be addressed in future works.

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Definitions and Abbreviations

Word, Phrase or Abbreviation	Definition or Expansion
DfT	Department for Transport
DfT	Department for transport
GPS	Global positioning system
iBike	Instrumented Bicycle
INS	Inertial navigation system
PTV	Stands for Planung Transport Verkehr which means Planning transport traffic and refers to the German company which developed the VISSIM software
TfL	Transport for London
TRL	Transport Research Laboratory
VISSIM	Traffic simulation software

Table 1 Definitions and Abbreviations

Chapter 1: Introduction

Congestion is one of the main transportation planning challenges. An average of 178 hours per year per driver in the UK is lost due to congestion, costing around £1,317 per driver per year (Reed and Kidd, 2019). Additionally, congestion can lead to other problems like air pollution. In London road transport generates about 50% of air pollution (MoL, 2019), affecting people's health. In order to tackle these problem governments worldwide are investing in cycling.

In the UK, the Cycling and Walking Investment Strategy is one of the measures the government has been taking to decrease congestion and therefore air pollution. Cycling and walking are sustainable modes of transport, however, cycling enables people to travel faster and longer distances. Cycling brings several benefits, for instance, environmental by reducing pollution. Social benefits by reducing congestion and therefore people travel times and stress (Hennessy & Wiesenthal, 1999). Cycling is also a very good form of exercise, people who cycle to work have a 46% lower risk of cardiovascular disease and 45% lower risk of developing cancer compared to those who drive or use public transport (Cycling UK, 2018). Nonetheless, encouraging people to cycle requires wider planning to understand how to accommodate the new demand on the traffic network and the cyclist behaviour on it.

According to the Cycling and Walking Investment Strategy, there will be more investment for cycling infrastructure. This investment aims to deliver safer, better integrated and more attractive routes for cycling. One advantage of cycling infrastructure is that a bicycle is smaller than a car. Therefore, needs narrower lanes which make it cheaper and less land consuming than cars' road network. However, planning is needed and being able to model different scenarios to prevent possible safety problems or simply visualize the optimal option.

A traffic simulation software allows transport planners to relate the network supply represented in roads and its characteristics, to the user's demand. Namely, an origin-destination flow matrix combined with a simulation of the choice behaviour of each journey (Gentile & Nökel, 2016). This relation produces particular traffic conditions on the network such as travel times, queues and even the price of the journey. Today's network complexity, the diverse transport modes and their interactions make the use of a traffic simulator almost indispensable before build or modify transport schemes. Consequently, traffic simulation software needs to be improved and calibrated to better imitate reality.

Copenhagen is one of the world's most bicycle-friendly cities (CDC, 2019). This was possible after building new cycling infrastructure, park areas and improvement of existing cycle roads' capacity. All these measures are simulated and assessed using PTV's VISSIM software (COWI, 2012). To develop the software further, a consulting group, COWI, was hired to study cycling behaviour for example speed, acceleration, following gap,

behaviour through bus stops and the effect on narrower lanes to the cyclist. PTV then used this study to develop and calibrate the VISSIM cycling model.

The PTV VISSIM microscopic traffic simulation software was first developed in 1992 and has since evolved into a global market leader. Traditionally it enabled the modelling of vehicle traffic at the individual vehicle level, but subsequent extensions have made the consideration of further types of road users possible notably public transport and more recently pedestrians. The most recent addition is the ability to simulate cyclists. The underlying theoretical model is based on a study that analysed the behaviour of real cyclists through the monitoring of their observed trajectories. However, this software tool was calibrated using trajectory data from Copenhagen, Denmark, and its applicability and relevance with respect to the UK context have not been assessed.

1.1 Aims and objectives

This research has seven key objectives. These objectives are steps that need to be followed through the project in order to objectively achieve the aim.

1. Identify previous studies where bicycle trajectories are studied and their used methodology.
2. Plan a field experiment through pre-designed scenarios in order to collect cyclist behaviour and trajectory data.
3. Build the same scenarios in VISSIM software and calibrate them using the recorded video from the iBike.
4. Extract, sort, and homogenize speed, acceleration and trajectory data from both real and simulated scenarios.
5. Determine whether the speed distribution collected from the iBike and the speed distribution simulated by VISSIM software are or not the same.
6. Determine whether the acceleration distribution collected from the iBike and the acceleration distribution simulated by VISSIM software are or not the same.
7. Identify the differences and limitations of the VISSIM's cyclist tool by comparing its simulation with the iBike reconstructed trajectory and video recorded.

The aim of this project is, therefore, to investigate the realism of the VISSIM cyclist model in the UK context. First, it will involve the collection of trajectory data through a field experiment with real cyclists riding an instrumented bicycle at selected sites in and around the University Southampton in semi-controlled condition scenarios (e.g. reaction to static objects, such as parked vehicles and street furniture). Then, it will entail simulating the corresponding scenarios in VISSIM and drawing comparisons between the real and simulated trajectories as to the realism of the latter.

1.2 Structure

The dissertation structure is as follows. Chapter 2 reviews prior researches about cycling modelling and cycling behaviour. Compares opinions about factors that change cycling behaviour, look at similar projects, methodologies that could be used and identifies the main limitations of the study. Chapter 3 explains in detail the followed methodology process used through this project. An explanation of why the methodology was chosen, pros and cons, who was involved in the project and how they were selected is given. Chapter 4 shows the results from the field experiment and its quality and reliability are discussed. Chapter 5 presents the findings of the study and its similarities with previous works mentioned in Chapter 2. Finally, Chapter 6 summarises the whole study, discusses the limitation of it and recommendations for future researches are made.

Chapter 2: Literature review

Cycling can be seen from different perspectives according to the society. While in low-economies cycling is seen as an obsolete mode of transport for those who cannot afford a car. High-economy countries see cycling as one solution to the saturated road-network. In countries with high car ownership, for instance, in northern Europe, governments are encouraging cycling (Horton et al., 2007). Although countries like Denmark, Netherlands and Germany now have a high percentage of cycling trips, the UK has not been that successful (Buehler and Pucher, 2012).

2.1 Cycling in the UK

Cycling has been on the upswing worldwide since 2007 (Colville-Andersen, 2018) and cycling strategies are not new in the UK. In 1996 the Conservative Government published a cycling strategy which aimed to double bicycle use by 2002 and quadruple by 2012 relative to 1996 (Horton et al., 2007). This target was not reached, indeed, In England from 2002 to 2018 the average number of trips has barely changed as shown in Figure 1. Nonetheless, the distance travelled has risen by 50%, this can be related to the recent inversion in bicycle facilities (e.g. Independent cycle lanes in London). The current Cycling and Walking Investment Strategy (2017) aims to double cycling trips by 2025.

Figure 1 Cycling trends (DfT, 2019, p4)

2.1.1 Facts

Only 2% of trips in the UK are done by cycling (DfT, 2019). Contrary, the Netherlands, Denmark and Germany are the countries with the highest percentage of cycling trips with 27%, 17% and 10% respectively (Harms and Kansen, 2018; Cycling, 2015). This might be related to the bicycle ownership as 90% of the population in Denmark own a bicycle (Cycling, 2015) whereas in the UK only 42% have access to a bicycle (DfT, 2019). In addition, in the mentioned countries, men and women cycle about the same number of trips and distances (Horton et al., 2007). However, in the UK men cycle 2.5 times more trips than women and travel 4 times

further. Commuting and leisure are the main purposes of these trips with 36% and 35% respectively (DfT, 2019).

Other important facts are car ownership where people without a car cycle more and further than those who have. In addition, UK people between 40-49 are the ones that cycle the most (DfT, 2019). Nonetheless, there are negative outcomes of cycling in the UK as casualties. Cycling is the second place in accidents per miles rate and is really close to the first which is motorcycling (see Figure 2). The number of cyclists seriously injured or killed increased by 29% in the past 10 years which is partially attributed to the rising cycling traffic which has increased by 17% in the same period (DfT, 2019).

Figure 2 Casualties by road user (DfT, 2019, p10)

As a result, the main obstacle to increasing cycled trips in the UK seems to be road safety concerns (DfT, 2018). The Cycling and Walking Investment Strategy (2017) establish some actions to tackle the barriers shown in Figure 3. These actions include financial investment, behaviour change, safety and partnership. Chiefly financial investment and safety plans are designated to improve and increase the cycle roads. Hence the importance of a traffic simulation software that allows studying the cycling interaction with other transport modes. In addition, it can prevent traffic problems and let alternatives schemes to be explored to then implement the optimal one.

Figure 3 Cycling barriers (DfT, 2018, p13)

2.2 Traffic Simulation Software

Traffic modelling is intended to simulate or forecast the transport modes interactions and behaviour on a street, junction or a wider area. Traffic simulation software is important for transportation planning as experimenting with real traffic is not practical neither safe. There is different software that has been developed and improved to make traffic modelling as accurate as possible. Some widely used traffic simulators include VISSIM, VISUM, SATURN, SUMO, S-Paramics, Dracula, Quadstone Paramics Modeller, Treiber's Microsimulation, Aimsun, Trafficware SimTraffic and CORSIM TRAFVU (Hawick, 2009; TRL, 2006). However, each software has its own advantages, disadvantages and specific applications.

Traffic simulation models can be classified into 3 categories microscopic, macroscopic and mesoscopic. Microscopic modelling is used for detailed traffic interactions and can bring parameters like delays, speed, flow and queue lengths (Nasuha et al., 2018). Macroscopic modelling is recommended when a larger area needs to be studied and detailed behaviour is not required, traffic characteristics such as speed, flow and density can be obtained. Mesoscopic modelling is a combination of microscopic and macroscopic where small groups parameters can be obtained. For the aims of this project, a microsimulation modelling is required to study in detail the cycling interaction and behaviour in controlled situations.

In the UK, just a few particular software is the most used according to the traffic modelling guidelines (TfL, 2010). In this guideline most used software for micro and macro simulation are mentioned. In microsimulation, which is studied in this research, VISSIM, S-Paramics and AIMSUN are highlighted. Nevertheless, only VISSIM has a dedicated section in the modelling guideline showing its importance. In fact, TfL streets traffic directorate recommends using VISSIM for building microsimulation models (TfL, 2010).

2.2.1 PTV's VISSIM

Currently, there are many traffic simulation software. However, VISSIM is the only one that can represent the interaction of every transport mode including cycling (PTV, 2019). "VISSIM is a microscopic, behaviour-based multi-purpose traffic simulation to analyse and optimize traffic flows" (Barceló, 2010). In Figure 4 it can be appreciated how the software can model bicycles, motorcycles and cars sharing the same road. This VISSIM tool has been used and calibrated to model traffic in Copenhagen, one of the most bicycle-friendly cities in the world, however, its use in a UK context has not been assessed yet.

Figure 4 VISSIM example model (PTV, 2019)

2.2.2 Copenhagen Project

Copenhagen is one of the most cycling-friendly cities in the world. This city had used VISSIM software to simulate motorized traffic. However, 41% of the population go to work or school by cycling (City of Copenhagen, 2017) and have a significant impact on circulation. Therefore, cycling traffic needed to be modelled with cycling behaviour as real as possible. In order to make it possible the city of Copenhagen hired COWI, a consulting group, to help them implement cyclist to the existent software.

The project was done in 2012 and PTV group collaborated with COWI by supplying the VISSIM software (COWI, 2012). COWI had two main objectives, the first was collecting, processing and studying data. The second was implementing and validating the results into a VISSIM cyclist model. COWI collected data using video recordings and GPS measurements, in addition, the city of Copenhagen provided traffic counts (COWI, 2013). They focused on ten relevant parameters in cyclist microsimulation.

2.2.3 Basic parameters

COWI divided the ten parameters into three categories. First, basic parameters which include vehicle characteristics, speed distribution and acceleration distribution. Second, parameters regarding bicycle paths, following, overtaking, behaviour at narrow section and behaviour at the bus stop. Last, parameters concerning intersections, behaviour in waiting zones, behaviour at stop lines and behaviour at right turns (COWI, 2013). However, due to the limitations of this research, only basic parameters were analysed.

For vehicle characteristics, they mainly looked at the bicycle size, using catalogues and manual measurements. The results were used to create the VISSIM 3D models of the bicycle as shown in Figure 5. Bicycle size between Copenhagen and the UK were assumed equal as they have been standardised and small variation is unlikely to affect the overall behaviour. Also, carrier bicycles and electric bikes were 3D modelled and added to the software. Nevertheless, only common bikes are used during this study and therefore used in the VISSIM models.

Figure 5 VISSIM's bicycle 3D models (COWI, 2013)

Next, speed distributions were obtained using the GPS measurements. They did all measurements in no rainy or windy days, so weather does not influence the results. Also, the speed data was collected during free-flow conditions to avoid alterations caused by congestion and traffic lights. They found that spread of speed distributions is significantly greater than the included in VISSIM. In addition, from the video recordings, a speed reduction was observed at turns.

Acceleration distributions data was also obtained by GPS measurements. VISSIM's bicycle acceleration distributions were based on cars accelerations. As it would be expected COWI found the acceleration is lower in bicycles and highlighted typical accelerations values between -2.93 m/s^2 and 1.52 m/s^2 (COWI, 2013). Both speed and acceleration distributions were incorporated to VISSIM. These results are shown in the following tables.

Speed (Km/h)	Cumulative %
14	0 %
18	9 %
22	44 %
26	77 %
30	93 %
35	100 %

Table 2 Speed distributions (COWI, 2013)

Speed (km/h)	Acceleration (m/s ²)
0,0	0,4
2,6	1,2
3,7	1,6
5,1	1,8
6,7	1,6
8,0	1,3
13,2	0,4
18,5	0,3
22,2	0,3
25,9	0,3
29,7	0,2
60,0	0,0

Table 3 Acceleration distribution (COWI, 2013)

Speed (km/h)	Deceleration (m/s ²)
0,0	-3,0
5,0	-4,0
20,0	-2,0
60,0	0,0

Table 4 Deceleration distribution (COWI, 2013)

Notice that the average speed from the distribution obtained seems to be higher than the average cycling speed. Bicycle average speed has founded to be about 15.5 km/h (Traffic Department, 2013) while the COWI results are above 20 km/h. This difference might be because of the way they measure the speed as they do not consider when people stop at road junctions, traffic lights or pedestrian crossings. In this project, the distribution obtained from Copenhagen was used. In addition, pedestrian speed was set as 5 km/h which is a typical average walking speed (Crabtree et al., 2014).

2.3 iBike

In order to assess the realism of VISSIM in a UK context, a precise trajectory data of real cycling behaviour should be obtained. A bicycle lane should have a minimum width of 1.5 m (TfL, 2016). Therefore, the technology used in this project to track the bicycle position must have an accuracy the closest to 1.5 m possible. Although there are technologies enough accurate like Ultra-wideband (UWB), it is not allowed to use outdoors. In contrast, there are some common and known technologies that are not precise enough like GPS, Wi-Fi and radio-frequency identification (RFID) (Milonidis et al., 2017). Therefore, the iBike, an available tool, is the one used in this project.

Figure 6 iBike (Milonidis et al., 2017)

The iBike is an instrumented bicycle (illustrated in Figure 6) with some sensors that record different data to later process it and output bicycle trajectory characteristics. Some characteristics that can be obtained and are useful to this research include time, coordinates, speed, acceleration and a reconstructed trajectory. This bike can get more accurate measures than GPS and INS. In addition, the iBike can video record its trajectory and therefore it can collect all data analysed in the Copenhagen project.

To obtain the reconstructed trajectory the iBike obtains raw data from 4 different sensors. These sensors measure the yaw angle and the distance covered by the rear wheel of the bicycle. Then, these data are collected by the Arduino microcontroller board. Next, the collected data is sent to either an SD card or a laptop. Subsequent, a data acquisition software saves it on a database in real-time this process is shown in Figure 7. For project purposes, the INS trajectory will be used.

Figure 7 iBike data process

Chapter 3: Methodology

As mentioned in Chapter 2 there are important parameters that need to be analysed from the VISSIM software. In order to do it, a field experiment around the University of Southampton was done. Twelve volunteers were asked to ride the iBike through a predefined route. Using the iBike, trajectory data was collected in addition to a video recording. Then, the datasets were processed to obtain the basic parameters, speed, acceleration and a reconstructed trajectory. Finally, the same route was modelled using VISSIM software to assess the differences between the real and modelled cyclist behaviour.

3.1 Field experiment

The field experiment was planned to be around the Highfield campus of the University of Southampton. This due to three reasons, first to make it safer as streets within the campus are low speed. Second, the iBike was kept in Boldrewood campus which is just about 1 km from Highfield campus and as a result, it was a convenient location. And finally, the campus had different roads with different characteristics (e.g. slope, width, condition) and therefore data from different scenarios was possible to analyse. The first step was to design the routes to be used.

3.1.1 Defining the route

A selection of sites with different characteristics around Highfield campus was identified. A bicycle is a dynamic vehicle, and therefore a variety of road types were looked for e.g. footpaths, cycle lanes, car lanes. Also, different features in each road e.g. slopes, wideness, road-condition. Five short routes where a combination of these characteristics appeared were chosen. However, after doing a pilot experiment one was removed due to the poor condition of the road that made an uncomfortable riding and could have brought problems to the iBike sensors.

The four short routes were apart from each other which needed to set four times the iBike to run the experiment. To make it smoother, easier for volunteers and to include points of interest for another research. A larger route containing the four small routes was defined, see Figure 8. The circuit began and ended at burgess road library bus stop, marked with a yellow circle. The complete route was completed in around 18 minutes by each participant.

Figure 8 Field experiment route, adapted from Google Maps (2019)

3.1.2 Volunteers

Participants were all University of Southampton students and members of the staff who used the bicycle as their main transport mode. Students were contacted using the university mail and were only accepted after confirming they mainly used a bicycle to commute. Staff members were personally approached after a cycling comfort group meeting. After giving details of the research and experiment to both students and staff, about 20 people were interested in participating. Then the dates to perform the experiment were planned.

The main limitations of the experiment were the weather and the volunteer's availability. The weather was a constraint in this research as the iBike, used to collect data, is not waterproof. Thus, a weather forecast was used where only no-rainy days were selected following the COWI's methodology. Another limitation was that Dr Shah Miah, who developed the iBike, was working in London and his support to run the experiment was needed. Hence, it was decided to divide the experiment only into two days where Dr Miah was available. Trying to fit volunteer's availability, a week-day and a weekend-day were chosen.

Chapter 3: Methodology

An online poll was sent through e-mail to all the potential participants. The poll was divided in the two days and in one-hour time-slots. This was the estimated time to explaining the volunteers the experiment and their role on it, in addition to the ridding time and data extraction. From this poll 11 people sign up to run the experiment. The volunteers were both genders and different ages which was positive in terms of data diversity.

3.1.3 Experiment days

Before the experiment, volunteers received an email with the route and a brief explanation of the iBike. To make it easier for them the route was intended to be marked with chalk and paper signs, but the University maintenance staff did not allow it. Instead, a student who knew the whole route rode a bike in front of each volunteer who was ridding the iBike. Then the volunteers only needed to follow him (see Figure 9). The change in the original way to do the experiment could affect the results, as the volunteers were not ridding totally free and could have been influenced by the student cycling behaviour

Figure 9 Field experiment

At the beginning and end of the ride, the iBike collection data system and the video camera were setups. The iBike also has a button that permits to put a marker in the data consequently, the volunteers were asked to press that button at the beginning and end of each route. To make it easy for them, the student riding in front let them know when exactly to press the button. The experiment was done following the risk assessment recommendations for wearing a cycling-helmet and a reflective-vest. Dr Miah Shah supervised and supported the use of the iBike.

3.2 VISSIM model

Models from the four small routes were created using VISSIM Software (see Figure 10). The software allows setting different modes of transport e.g. buses, cars, pedestrians, heavy vehicles, trams. Roads have several features that can be changed for instance desire speed, width, gradient, behaviour within it, number of lanes and even restrict specific vehicles. However, only road-lanes and modes of transport directly involved in the experiment were considered. In addition, 3D objects to make a better visualization can be added nevertheless for the purposes of this research this tool was not used.

Figure 10 VISSIM's interface

In chapter 2 the average speed of pedestrian and cyclist in the UK were mentioned. VISSIM offers a range of different desire speeds distributions, thus the closest speeds to the literature ones were selected for pedestrians and while for cars, street speed limits were used. Road's gradients were estimated using google earth tools. Lanes' width was calculated using both google maps and Bing maps. Nonetheless, after running the experiment, the four models were calibrated to make them closer to reality, by using the recorded video from the iBike.

The first route has all the features previously mentioned, it started and ended in the yellow circle (See Figure 11). The route starts on a road with a car-lane and bicycle-lane going downhill. Next, it has a single-lane road used by pedestrians, bicycles and cars. Then it goes through road with pedestrian-lane and bicycle-lane going uphill. After, a wide footpath where bicycles usually ride on. Finally, it goes through a road with car and bicycle lanes again.

Figure 11 Route 1 model, adapted from VISSIM

The second route (Figure 12) started at the first route ending and had some of the characteristics of the first route. It starts with the same road with a car-lane and a bicycle-lane downhill. Then it turns to the opposite way in a two-ways single-lane, which is not possible to model in VISSIM. And it finishes with a single-lane road with car park space by the sides. Parked cars were not modelled because they did not seem to have an effect on the cyclist within the designed routes.

turnings to the left and right. This allows studying the cyclist turning behaviour when they have no lane or other vehicles restrictions.

Figure 14 Route 4, adapted from VISSIM

3.3 Data

3.3.1 Collection

Data was collected from the iBike which brings two different files. The information coming from the sensors and the INS are saved in a CSV file. This file contains 36 columns of the different measurements taken e.g. INS latitude, INS longitude, time, marked points, steering angle (see Table 36). Each row is from a different moment/time, the iBike writes between 40-50 rows/second. The second file comes from the video camera that saves an FHD video in an MP4 file.

At the end of the experiment, there were two files for each participant. The CSV file was used to estimate the basic parameters to compare with the ones in the VISSIM software. In addition, a reconstructed trajectory was also calculated from the CSV file to compare it with one of the VISSIM model output. The video was used to calibrate the modelling (see Figure 15). Also, the video was used to observe and analyse the cyclist behaviour at specific moments such as turnings or when avoiding an obstacle.

Figure 15 Model Calibration. Left – video recording photogram, right – VISSIM model screenshot

3.3.2 Sorting

As expected, volunteers missed some starting and endpoints. Therefore, before analysing the data, it was sorted using both the marking points and the video recording as a reference. Each CSV file was converted to XLSX file, to easily manipulate it, and data corresponding to each of the four small routes was identified and extracted from the complete file. Once having data from each participant divided into the four smaller datasets, the reconstructed trajectory was obtained using INS coordinates. Also, these datasets were used to calculate the speed and acceleration.

To obtain speed, Hall Effect gear tooth sensor from the iBike which can detect spoke magnets installed on the wheel was used. This sensor counts the spoke magnets passing through it (see Figure 6) and then saves it in the iBike_PulseCount column. Using this counting and the time recorded saved in the iBike_PulseTime column, change in distance and time can be obtained and therefore the speed using the formulas below. Wheel diameter and the number of spokes are constant and were obtained directly from the iBike resulting in 0.64 m and 18 respectively. Finally, using the speed values and the time again, acceleration was obtained with its known formula.

$$Arc\ length = \frac{\pi * Diameter}{Number\ of\ spoke\ magnets}$$

$$\Delta Distance = Arc\ length * (PulseCount_n - PulseCount_{n-1})$$

$$Speed = \frac{\Delta Distance}{PulseTime_n - PulseTime_{n-1}}$$

3.3.3 Analysis

A comparison between data collected from the iBike and the output from VISSIM software was done. First VISSIM software can output a vehicle record with several characteristics. However, for the purpose of this research only simulation time, rear coordinates, speed and acceleration were obtained. To make it more

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realistic this process was repeated as many times as volunteers using different seeds. Having at the end the same number of datasets from each route model than from the iBike.

Next, speed and acceleration data were merged per route. Having now just 2 files for each route, one from the VISSIM model and one from the iBike. Following, data sets needed to be homologized in order to compare them. Speed was calculated in kilometres per hour as is the standard unit while the acceleration was set in metres per second. Finally, speed and acceleration distributions were compared using SPSS software.

Coordinates from VISSIM and iBike were converted into Universal Transverse Mercator coordinate system. This was plotted to see the notorious differences between the model and the real data. Then these smaller locations were analysed in deep. From iBike data using the video recording and from the model using its 3D animation. Results are shown in the following chapter.

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From the 11 volunteers that did the field experiment only 8 complete data from each route were obtained. Consequently, 8 different seeds were used in each route inside the VISSIM software. The 8 data from iBike were merged and the same was done with VISSIM data. Each route merged data were compared and analysed chiefly using SPSS software. However, in some cases data for a single volunteer/seed was used for reasons explained below.

4.1 Route 1

4.1.1 Speed

First, speed over time through this route was observed. Nonetheless, after plotting some data it was noticed that most of the volunteers stopped once through this route (see Figure 1). After watching the video recordings, it was founded this stop was caused by a traffic light on the route. This stop strongly affects the speed average which is an important statistics measure for this research. Hence, a data sample with no stops was looked for both VISSIM and iBike.

Figure 16 Route 1 – Speed over time with a stop

After one sample of each real and simulated data with no stop was founded, they were analysed. From Figure 17 and Figure 18, it looks like VISSIM has higher speed and consequently, the route was finished in less time. In addition, measurements from iBike seem to have larger variance. While speed average looked larger in

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VISSIM but closer to 15 km/h in the iBike. Despite VISSIM desire speed was set as 15 km/h as it was the nearer to the 15.5 km/h mentioned in the literature review.

Figure 17 Route 1 – iBike – Speed over time

Figure 18 Route 1 – VISSIM – Speed over time

From these samples, mean, standard deviation, variance and percentiles were obtained. In Table 5 it can be appreciated that speed means is higher in VISSIM, but the variance is lower. Maximum speeds are similar

while the minimum is significantly different. However, these are measurements from just one sample and 8 different data is available. Next, a comparison between the whole data was done.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	7418	2724
Mean		14.8065	18.3393
Std. Deviation		2.16679	1.02414
Variance		4.695	1.049
Minimum		9.52	16.33
Maximum		19.38	21.24
Percentiles	5	11.0390	16.6500
	25	13.1390	17.4200
	50	15.2050	18.8000
	75	16.3720	18.8600
	95	18.1000	20.1000

Table 5 Route 1 – Speed descriptive statistics 1

Table 6 shows descriptive statistics from the whole data of both iBike and VISSIM. Average speed is lower than from samples caused by the stops through the route (see Figure 19). However, the fifth percentile is lower in iBike and vastly lower in VISSIM as it went from 16.65 to 1.81. This change in the results can be explained by how speed is calculated in the iBike, where when it stops, speed output is an invalid value and therefore, zeros are not counted (see Figure 19). In order to get more realistic results and closer to the Copenhagen experiment, where only cycling in free flow was studied, zeros from VISSIM were removed.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	65826	25438
	Missing	25438	65826
Mean		13.2497	15.7112
Std. Deviation		2.73059	4.11414
Variance		7.456	16.926
Minimum		.04	.00
Maximum		22.38	21.24
Percentiles	5	8.9500	1.8100
	25	11.6000	15.2800
	50	13.4400	16.4700
	75	14.9800	18.0700
	95	17.3100	18.9000

Table 6 Route 1 – Speed descriptive statistics 2

Figure 19 Route 1 - Speed distribution iBike/VISSIM

After removing zeros statistics values became closer to the ones from the reference sample as shown in Table 7. From this table, it can be appreciated that standard deviation, after using different seeds and volunteers, increased. Although, this increase is more notorious in VISSIM, from 1.024 to 2.478 than in iBike, from 2.167 to 2.731. Speed data from VISSIM and the iBike had then a similar standard deviation through the first route. While the mean kept higher in VISSIM simulation, so a mean comparison was done in order to verify whether they are or not equal.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM_no_0
N	Valid	65826	24348
	Missing	25438	66916
Mean		13.2497	16.4146
Std. Deviation		2.73059	2.47755
Variance		7.456	6.138
Minimum		.04	.01
Maximum		22.38	21.24
Percentiles	5	8.9500	13.3445
	25	11.6000	15.4300
	50	13.4400	16.6400
	75	14.9800	18.1500
	95	17.3100	18.9500

Table 7 Route 1 – Speed descriptive statistics 3

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Due to the large sample size, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, therefore Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Subsequently, such test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 8 below.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Speed	Equal variances assumed	1041.533	.000	-158.344	90172	.000	-3.16482	.01999	-3.20399	-3.12565
	Equal variances not assumed			-165.569	47586.725	.000	-3.16482	.01911	-3.20229	-3.12736

Table 8 Route 1 - Speed T-test

4.1.2 Acceleration

Following the same order as speed distribution, first acceleration distribution over time was observed from a single volunteer and seed. In Figure 20 it seems that accelerations in iBike have a larger variance than in VISSIM (see Figure 21). Also, from Figure 21 a continuous acceleration of 0 m/s² between seconds 75-100 which is very unlikely to happen. There are factors like road-slope or wind that will give positive or negative acceleration to the bike even when the cyclist is no pedalling. Likewise, in iBike's graph, no horizontal lines can be appreciated as in the VISSIM's graph which could lead to unrealistic cyclist behaviour.

Figure 20 Route 1 – iBike – Acceleration over time

Figure 21 Route 1 – iBike – Acceleration over time

Descriptive statistics were obtained from these samples. In Table 9, a larger variance in iBike is confirmed, 0.14 against 0.23 from VISSIM. Minimum values are similar while the maximum value is almost double in iBike than in VISSIM. This maximum and minimum values are within literature values, 1.52 m/s² and -2.93 m/s². Looking at percentiles, symmetric distributions around zero can be expected.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	7417	2724
Mean		.0167	-.0023
Std. Deviation		.37471	.15130
Variance		.140	.023
Minimum		-1.43	-1.41
Maximum		1.54	.90
Percentiles	5	-.5960	-.1900
	25	-.2070	-.0600
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2510	.0400
	95	.6351	.1900

Table 9 Route 1 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 1

Once observed a singular case, the whole data was analysed as shown in Table 10. First, similar average, close to zero, between iBike and VISSIM can be noticed. Minimum values are similar and valid as discussed in

literature whereas maximum values are higher than expected. Nonetheless, these values are outliers and from percentiles, it can be observed that most of the observations are between -0.54 and 0.57 in the iBike and -0.30 and 0.30 in VISSIM. Finally, the standard deviation is almost the same.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	65557	25438
Mean		.0133	.0016
Std. Deviation		.34678	.34571
Variance		.120	.120
Minimum		-2.05	-2.34
Maximum		4.86	3.40
Percentiles	5	-.5400	-.3000
	25	-.1900	-.0700
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2200	.0500
	95	.5700	.3000

Table 10 Route 1 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 2

Then an illustrated comparison between iBike and VISSIM acceleration distributions was done and as shown in Figure 22. In this graph, a more spread distribution from iBike can be appreciated. Also, it can be noticed that more than 40% of observations in VISSIM are really close to zero while in the iBike it is less than 20%. Both measurements seem to follow a normal distribution with a similar average. Therefore, a T-Test to evaluate the similarity of acceleration distributions was done.

Figure 22 Route 1 - Acceleration distribution iBike/VISSIM

As it was previously mentioned, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, consequently, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average acceleration between iBike and VISSIM. Next, such test found significant evidence that the average accelerations were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 11 below.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Acceleration	Equal variances assumed	3699.952	.000	4.593	90993	.000	.01175	.00256	.00674	.01677
	Equal variances not assumed			4.599	46430.234	.000	.01175	.00256	.00674	.01676

Table 11 Route 1 - Acceleration T-test

4.1.3 Trajectory

At the beginning of the first route, some limitations of VISSIM appeared. As shown in Figure 23 the road has a cycle lane and a car lane but with opposite ways. This cannot be model in VISSIM as it only allows one-way links. In a link you can decide its behaviour (Urban, right-side rule, free-way, footpath and cycle-track), the number of lanes and its widths, however, you cannot choose independent behaviour for each lane. For this part of the route, the road was modelled as two links, but this is not realistic because vehicles in different links do not interact between them e.g. a cyclist can go through a car and nothing will happen.

Figure 23 Route 1 - Opposite flows

Another common scenario found in cyclist routes is obstructions, in this case, a bollard on the cycle lane (left side). This caused most of the volunteers to change to the pedestrian lane while in VISSIM simulation they kept in the same lane because no real obstacles were able to model. VISSIM does have a tool to insert obstacles nonetheless these obstacles do not interact with the vehicles as shown in Figure 24. In the UK, cycle barriers where cyclists are forced to dismount their bikes are common. Therefore, on-road obstacles can be a good idea to implement in future VISSIM updates.

Figure 24 Route 1 - On-road obstacle, left picture obtained from VISSIM software.

In Figure 25, two cyclist riding in contrary directions on a narrow lane can be observed. Around Highfield campus and in more places in the UK there are two-way cycle lanes and some of them are narrow even for bikes making cyclist invade other lanes or stop. In this picture, it can be noticed how the second cyclist was forced to move to the pedestrian lane. This behaviour cannot be model in VISSIM software because there are only one-way links. Cycling overtaking has a similar behaviour as the slower cyclist keeps on his left to let the other overtake as in this picture the followed cyclist does then, it might be considered in the implementation of two-way links.

Figure 25 Route 1 - Two-way cycle lane

Looking at the trajectories the iBike and the simulated bike followed, a good representation of reality can be appreciated. The main differences were found at turnings. Before and after turning cyclists tended to be a little further from the curb as it can be observed in Figure 26 while VISSIM simulation kept a constant distance from the curb. In addition, cyclist tried to take the shortest way when the road is width enough as in the northern and eastern parts of the route. Cyclist behaviour at turnings, especially distance to the curb, can be important in cyclist infrastructure planning and design and therefore relevant in VISSIM software.

Figure 26 Route 1 - Trajectories

4.2 Route 2

4.2.1 Speed

First, speed over time graph was done to observe the speed changes through the route and select volunteer data with no stops (see Figure 27). Although there were no stops during the route the speed fell to 7 km/h

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which is significantly lower than the cyclist average speed. After watching the video recording it was noticed that at the beginning of the route it was mainly downhill and from second 50 until 90 the volunteer was going uphill, finishing in a level surface. This slope changes explain these speed increases and decreases. Contrary, in Figure 28 a speed more constant and closer to 15.5 km/h was found, even when road gradients were included in the model they did not have as much effect as in real life.

Figure 27 Route 2 – iBike – Speed over time

Figure 28 Route 2 – VISSIM – Speed over time

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Next, descriptive statistics were obtained to compare speeds more detailed. Looking at Table 12 it can be observed that speed means in notably higher in VISSIM than in the iBike, while variance is lower. Minimum values are considerably different, 6.31 and 12.77 km/h, this can suggest that VISSIM is not having an accurate representation of speed while riding uphill. On the other hand, maximum values are closer but still higher in VISSIM simulation. Similarly, to route 1, speed seems to be higher in the VISSIM model nonetheless a comparison between whole data was done.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	5587	2011
Mean		11.6134	15.2469
Std. Deviation		2.12009	1.13694
Variance		4.495	1.293
Minimum		6.31	12.77
Maximum		15.50	17.74
Percentiles	5	7.5500	13.1000
	25	9.8850	14.8300
	50	12.0040	15.2800
	75	13.1910	15.6100
	95	14.7020	17.3500

Table 12 Route 2 – Speed descriptive statistics 1

From Table 13 a minimum speed of 2.29 km/h was found. After watching the video recordings, it was noticed that the low speed happened when a car was coming toward the iBike in a single lane road at the end of the route. A low value was also found in the VISSIM data, 4.43 km/h, likewise in the simulation, it was caused due to a car in the same part of the route which demonstrates a good reality representation. VISSIM shows a higher maximum speed but the iBike's maximum value is close. Average speed keeps higher in VISSIM simulation, but this time was almost the same value as in literature. Besides the standard deviation keeps higher in the iBike.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	44071	15729
Mean		12.7659	15.5989
Std. Deviation		2.82791	1.63376
Variance		7.997	2.669
Minimum		2.29	4.43
Maximum		20.11	20.59
Percentiles	5	7.2400	12.9650
	25	11.4700	14.5100
	50	12.9700	15.3500
	75	14.5400	16.8900
	95	17.0200	18.0700

Table 13 Route 2 – Speed descriptive statistics 2

Speed distributions can be better appreciated in Figure 29 where apparently VISSIM simulation was faster but with less variance. In order to confirm the differences in distributions a T-test was done, the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed due to central limit theorem. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, therefore Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Then, such test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 14.

Population Pyramid Frequency Speed (Km/h) by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 29 Route 2 - Speed distribution iBike/VISSIM

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Speed	Equal variances assumed	2565.875	.000	-118.767	59798	.000	-2.83303	.02385	-2.87979	-2.78628
	Equal variances not assumed			-151.183	47830.030	.000	-2.83303	.01874	-2.86976	-2.79630

Table 14 Route 2 - Speed T-test

4.2.2 Acceleration

To start analysing route 2 acceleration, charts of acceleration over time from one volunteer and one seed were plotted (see Figure 30 and Figure 31). The first thing that can be appreciated is the change in variance between the iBike and VISSIM where the iBike look to have more variance. Also, in VISSIM a peak acceleration close to 2 m/s² is visible and is unusual as the rest of the graph seems to even have a pattern from second 60 onwards wherein the iBike its variation is more random. Both datasets measurements go over and under zero regularly and therefore an average close to zero is expected. Finally, two periods of around 20 seconds in VISSIM graph, 0 to 20 and 40 to 60, are straight lines which mean that acceleration remained constant with a value of zero, however, in the iBike’s diagram horizontal lines does not appear not even in short intervals suggesting an unrealistic software interpretation.

Figure 30 Route 2 – iBike – Acceleration over time

Figure 31 Route 2 – VISSIM – Acceleration over time

Next, descriptive statistics from the same datasets were obtained and are shown in Table 15. From the table, similarities were observed i.e. the variance 0.76 and 0.71, the maximum value 1.72 and 1.92 and the medium which is zero in both cases. The greatest difference is the minimum value with a -1.47 in the iBike against -0.32 in VISSIM this is maybe too little considering that the second part of the route is all uphill in addition to the turning after the downhill where cyclist tended to break. Means are slightly different both are close to zero as expected. Finally, looking at VISSIM’s percentiles data looks symmetrical, also 5th and 25th are equal as well as the 75th and 95th while they are completely different in the iBike.

		Statistics	
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	5586	2011
Mean		.0203	.0005
Std. Deviation		.27579	.26669
Variance		.076	.071
Minimum		-1.47	-.32
Maximum		1.72	1.92
Percentiles	5	-.4206	-.3200
	25	-.1400	-.3200
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.1890	.3200
	95	.4676	.3200

Table 15 Route 2 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 1

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Subsequent, the complete datasets from route 2 were analysed obtaining descriptive statistics (see Table 16) and an acceleration distributions chart (see Figure 32). From the table, a larger variance in the iBike was notice, similar minimum values and slightly higher maximum value in the iBike. The mean in both cases is almost zero as well as their medium. From the graph, a more spread data in the iBike is appreciated, while in VISSIM most of the values are concentrated between -0.1 and 0.1. Both datasets give the impression to follow a normal distribution, and that their distributions are different.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	44086	15730
Mean		.0078	.0020
Std. Deviation		.33327	.21162
Variance		.111	.045
Minimum		-1.53	-1.75
Maximum		3.67	2.88
Percentiles	5	-.5200	-.2900
	25	-.2000	-.0700
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2100	.0800
	95	.5600	.3000

Table 16 Route 2 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 2

Population Pyramid Frequency Acceleration by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 32 Route 2 - Acceleration distribution iBike/VISSIM

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Due to the sample size central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, subsequently, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average acceleration between iBike and VISSIM. Next, such test found significant evidence that the average accelerations were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 17 below.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Acceleration	Equal variances assumed	4201.914	.000	-39.667	60393	.000	-.53991	.01361	-.56659	-.51323
	Equal variances not assumed			-23.969	15893.168	.000	-.53991	.02253	-.58406	-.49576

Table 17 Route 2 - Acceleration T-test

4.2.3 Trajectory

Route two shares the beginning with the first route where some limitations were already mentioned (see Figure 23). After, a similar problem was found as illustrated in Figure 33. There is a single two-way lane road and therefore cyclist tended to stay to their left. Contrary, in VISSIM only one-way links can be modelled and as a result when any position in the link was selected cyclist could not consider the opposite flow in its behaviour. Nonetheless, this can be solved by selecting "left" in the desired lateral position of the driving behaviour option.

Figure 33 Route 2 - Two-way road. Left picture obtained from VISSIM software

In addition, later in this route, another conflict was found. Again, the problem was that no two directions lanes can be model and therefore no interaction between vehicles in opposite flows is simulated. In Figure 34 a car coming to the cyclist can be appreciated. In the VISSIM simulation, cyclist simply passes through the car with no reaction of any of them as links were overlaid. On the other hand, a cyclist riding the iBike slowed down his speed and kept to the right while the car was passing through.

Figure 34 Route 2 - Through a car. Left picture obtained from VISSIM software

Apart from the two-way lane, VISSIM software did a good simulation of this route by slowing down at turns, and its position on the road through the route. A reconstructed trajectory was obtained by using VISSIM and iBike coordinates and the result is shown in Figure 35. VISSIM trajectory looks to mostly go in a straight line while in the iBike it has small variations in the steering angle. However, the difference between trajectories can be the product of the inaccuracy of the INS sensors from the iBike in addition to the inaccuracy of Bing maps in VISSIM.

Figure 35 Route 2 – Reconstructed Trajectories. Map created with GPS Visualizer

4.3 Route 3

4.3.1 Speed

Speed over time in route 3 was observed and compared using a dataset from a volunteer and a seed. As in the previous routes speed in the iBike goes up and down with no clear pattern while in VISSIM tends to be more constant and the variations seem to follow a trend (see Figure 36 and Figure 37). At the end of this route, there is an uphill with a great gradient this can explain the speed drop that reaches its bottom around the second 140th in the iBike. Contrary, VISSIM graph keeps constant all the second half which is unrealistic. In addition, VISSIM simulation seems to be quite faster as it finishes in little more than 100 seconds while the iBike took over 150 seconds.

Figure 36 Route 3 – iBike – Speed over time

Figure 37 Route 3 – VISSIM – Speed over time

From the descriptive statistics in Table 18, it can be appreciated a significant difference in speed average, 11.16 km/h in iBike and 16.81 in VISSIM. Variance and range are greater in the iBike, maximum values are similar, but the minimum values are completely different. From the percentiles, the difference between the distributions is more notorious as in iBike dataset less than 25% observations are above 14 km/h while in VISSIM more than 95% are. VISSIM does not seem to well interpret the change in speed when the steep road is model.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	6735	2071
Mean		11.1599	16.8070
Std. Deviation		3.61243	1.55346
Variance		13.050	2.413
Minimum		3.97	13.84
Maximum		20.11	19.64
Percentiles	5	5.5680	14.9300
	25	8.4980	15.0800
	50	11.0710	18.1600
	75	13.9210	18.1600
	95	17.0530	18.1700

Table 18 Route 3 – Speed descriptive statistics 1

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Comparing the complete datasets from the iBike and VISSIM is notorious that this routing model was the less realistic of all four. Average speed is about 50% higher in VISSIM than in the iBike (see Table 19). The range and standard deviation are significantly greater in the iBike this extremely high and low speeds can be the product of the steep road. In Figure 38 shows how iBike speed observations are spread wider than in VISSIM where observations are chiefly concentrated in 15 and 18 km/h. In this route speed distributions look do not look similar at all however, a T-test was conducted in order to confirm it.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	50014	16778
Mean		11.0477	16.5918
Std. Deviation		4.74233	1.39386
Variance		22.490	1.943
Minimum		.17	4.97
Maximum		27.87	21.03
Percentiles	5	4.6000	15.0800
	25	7.5700	15.2800
	50	10.1900	16.2000
	75	14.0900	17.6800
	95	20.0100	18.8600

Table 19 Route 3 – Speed descriptive statistics 2

Population Pyramid Frequency Speed by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 38 Route 3 - Speed distribution iBike/VISSIM

Due to the large sample size, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly

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different at 5% significance level, then Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Later, such test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 20 below.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		Independent Samples Test					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Speed	Equal variances assumed	13546.546	.000	-149.281	66790	.000	-5.54410	.03714	-5.61689	-5.47131
	Equal variances not assumed			-233.146	66033.913	.000	-5.54410	.02378	-5.59071	-5.49749

Table 20 Route 3 - Speed T-test

4.3.2 Acceleration

A comparison of acceleration overtime was done. Values and variation between the iBike and VISSIM seem to be similar in the first half but then VISSIM’s acceleration kept equal to zero in the second half of the route (see Figure 39 and Figure 40). These results were not expected as the route 3 goes through a cycle lane and then return over the same lane, therefore, accelerations in the second half were expected to be like a mirror projection of the first. Moreover, deceleration in at the end of the route was anticipated because of the prominent gradient of the lane. Consequently, VISSIM acceleration distribution does not illustrate the real behaviour of the bike mainly in the second half of this route.

Figure 39 Route 3 – iBike – Acceleration over time

Figure 40 Route 3 – VISSIM – Acceleration over time

Later descriptive statistics of the volunteer and seed datasets were obtained as shown in Table 21. From this table low standard deviation is appreciated in both cases in addition, the mean in is almost zero. A notable difference was obtained in the minimum value, -1.90 in the iBike and -0.37 in VISSIM, the latest is a little unrealistic considering the gradients of the route. In contrast, maximum values are similar but the obtained in VISSIM is greater. Finally, from percentiles, it can be appreciated how at least 25% of the observations are zero which is unlikely to happen.

		Statistics	
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	6734	2071
Mean		.0055	.0080
Std. Deviation		.40038	.27552
Variance		.160	.076
Minimum		-1.90	-.37
Maximum		1.74	2.01
Percentiles	5	-.6300	-.2500
	25	-.2120	-.1500
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2170	.0000
	95	.6690	.4500

Table 21 Route 3 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 1

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Next distributions, from the whole datasets of the route, were analysed. From Table 22, really similar standard deviations, compared with Table 21, were obtained which can suggest that results were more constants in this route. Acceleration average again is close to zero in both cases nonetheless in the iBike a little higher than in VISSIM. Looking at the percentiles and Figure 41, it can be appreciated that in VISSIM most of the observations are zero while in the iBike is only less than 20%. Finally, the iBike dataset looks to follow a normal distribution while in VISSIM not.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	49531	16778
Mean		.0077	.0039
Std. Deviation		.40307	.28166
Variance		.162	.079
Minimum		-2.84	-5.47
Maximum		2.99	3.09
Percentiles	5	-.6400	-.2500
	25	-.2000	.0000
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2100	.0000
	95	.6700	.4500

Table 22 Route 3 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 2

Population Pyramid Frequency Acceleration by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 41 Route 3 - Acceleration distribution iBike/VISSIM

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As it was previously mentioned, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, therefore, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average acceleration between iBike and VISSIM. Following, such test found there is no significant evidence from these datasets to suggest that the average accelerations are not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 23.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Acceleration	Equal variances assumed	5048.154	.000	1.122	66307	.262	.00377	.00336	-.00282	.01035
	Equal variances not assumed			1.332	41382.209	.183	.00377	.00283	-.00178	.00932

Table 23 Route 3 - Acceleration T-test

4.3.3 Trajectory

In route 3 the problem of the two-way cycle and pedestrian lane was identified, and the route was modelled using 2 overlaid links. This produced an unrealistic result as people and bicycles coming in opposite directions did not interact between them while in real life they do interact. In Figure 42 it can be appreciated how the cyclist is forced to use the walking path because a person is on the cycle lane. In the same picture but in the VISSIM simulation people lightly overlaid can be observed as they are walking in opposite directions and therefore no interaction is simulated.

Figure 42 Route 3 – Interaction. Left picture obtained from VISSIM software.

Another noticed limitation of VISSIM software in this route was standing people on the cycle lane. As an obstruction in a lane, people standing on the lane are an obstruction to the cyclist which then need to deviate to avoid them. In Figure 43 it can be observed a man standing in the cycle lane and at the back a group of people also obstructing the lane which made the cyclist move to the pedestrian lane. Being able to simulate standing people can help to build more realistic scenarios.

Figure 43 Route 3 - Standing people

Reconstructed trajectories from VISSIM and the iBike were obtained and are shown in Figure 44. In the first half of the route both routes seem to follow the correct path however in the comeback the iBike seem inaccurate. Nonetheless, it can still be observed a little change of the steering angle even in the straight parts of the route while in VISSIM line are straight. In this route behaviour at turning look similar in the iBike and VISSIM. This can be a result of the narrow cycle lane which does not let the cyclist plentiful space to freely move.

Figure 44 Route 3 – Reconstructed trajectories. Map created with GPS Visualizer

4.4 Route 4

4.4.1 Speed

In route 4 a lower speed variance was expected as the level through this route is almost constant. In Figure 45 a chart of the speed over time illustrates that iBike's speed is always under 15 km/h probably due to the

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short straight lines in the route. On the other hand, VISSIM's speed keeps over 15 km/h most of the time (see Figure 46). Variation of the speed looks similar in both cases and can be caused by the various turns in this route. Finally, low speeds under 10 km/h can be observed in the iBike at the beginning and end of the route but in VISSIM speed never went that low.

Figure 45 Route 4 – iBike – Speed over time

Figure 46 Route 4 – VISSIM – Speed over time

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From the descriptive statistics of these volunteer and seed trajectories, a close standard deviation is observed. The average speed is significantly higher in VISSIM than the iBike, 17.21 to 11.37 km/h. This result can be a product of the speed calibration in VISSIM using free-flow conditions and therefore a lower desire speed should be used in car parks and comparable locations. From the table, relatively lower minimum and maximum values were found in the iBike. However, to make a better comparison considering variations from the different volunteers and seeds, the whole datasets were used.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	2851	936
Mean		11.3664	17.2074
Std. Deviation		1.80697	1.85909
Variance		3.265	3.456
Minimum		5.82	12.77
Maximum		13.88	19.77
Percentiles	5	6.5920	13.3755
	25	10.8030	16.3875
	50	11.5230	17.2900
	75	12.7230	18.6900
	95	13.5022	19.7400

Table 24 Route 4 – Speed descriptive statistics 1

Speed distribution descriptive statistics from the iBike and VISSIM datasets are shown in Table 25. From the table, the consistent average speed was observed where VISSIM is almost 40% faster than the iBike. Standard deviation was greater in the iBike but still close while minimum and maximum values are significantly different. From Figure 47, it can be observed that both distributions seem to follow a normal distribution, in both cases a little negative skewed. Distributions' shape is similar but iBike's range is a wider and the speed values are lower.

Statistics			
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	21353	7861
Mean		11.8515	16.4012
Std. Deviation		2.01014	1.72118
Variance		4.041	2.962
Minimum		5.05	12.14
Maximum		16.41	20.62
Percentiles	5	7.8500	13.4000
	25	10.9700	15.2900
	50	12.0000	16.5500
	75	13.1000	17.5200
	95	15.0400	19.2200

Table 25 Route 4 – Speed descriptive statistics 2

Population Pyramid Frequency Speed by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 47 Route 4 - Speed distribution iBike/VISSIM

Due to the large sample size, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, then Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Later, such test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 26.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Speed	Equal variances assumed	35.542	.000	-178.076	29212	.000	-4.54968	.02555	-4.59976	-4.49961
	Equal variances not assumed			-191.223	16229.068	.000	-4.54968	.02379	-4.59632	-4.50305

Table 26 Route 4 - Speed T-test

4.4.2 Acceleration

Acceleration in route 4 had a smaller variance than previous routes as it can be appreciated in Figure 48 Figure 49. These lower variations might be related to being the shortest route and the almost inexistent gradient through it. From VISSIM graph it was noticed an acceleration increase after turnings and a deceleration just before turnings which is a natural cyclist behaviour observed in the volunteers. However, from the volunteer graph more variations were obtained while in VISSIM some horizontal lines still appeared. Finally, a rare acceleration behaviour can be noticed from the second twenty this happened during a turning but in the previous and following turning this was not repeated.

Figure 48 Route 4 – iBike – Acceleration over time

Figure 49 Route 4 – VISSIM – Acceleration over time

Descriptive statistics from these samples were obtained and are shown in Table 27. Acceleration range from the samples is the smallest from the 4 routes due to the previously mentioned. Acceleration means in both cases is as expected close to zero however in VISSIM is a negative value. From percentiles, it looks like both samples are symmetrical which and suggest that follow a normal distribution. Standard deviation in both cases is relatively low but significantly higher in the iBike, around 35%.

		Statistics	
		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	2850	936
Mean		.0056	-.0087
Std. Deviation		.27039	.19594
Variance		.073	.038
Minimum		-1.02	-.32
Maximum		1.21	.32
Percentiles	5	-.4410	-.3200
	25	-.1672	-.0900
	50	.0000	-.0100
	75	.1760	.1000
	95	.4594	.3200

Table 27 Route 4 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 1

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After analysing the samples, the whole datasets were used to obtain Table 28 and Figure 50. From the table similar acceleration means, and standard deviations are observed. Minimum values are the higher of the 4 routes while maximum values are the lowest. From the chart, similar acceleration distributions can be observed where VISSIM is a little more concentrated around zero. In order to see whether acceleration distributions are or not the same a T-test was done.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	21339	7861
Mean		.0119	.0006
Std. Deviation		.27735	.16811
Variance		.077	.028
Minimum		-1.23	-.32
Maximum		1.54	.70
Percentiles	5	-.4400	-.2800
	25	-.1600	-.0800
	50	.0000	-.0200
	75	.1800	.1000
	95	.4600	.3000

Table 28 Route 4 – Acceleration descriptive statistics 2

Population Pyramid Frequency Acceleration by iBike/VISSIM

Figure 50 Route 4 - Acceleration distribution iBike/VISSIM

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As previously mentioned, central limit theorem applies and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, consequently, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average acceleration between iBike and VISSIM. Next, such test found significant evidence that the average accelerations were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 29.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Acceleration	Equal variances assumed	1587.216	.000	3.415	29198	.001	.01138	.00333	.00485	.01792
	Equal variances not assumed			4.242	23004.783	.000	.01138	.00268	.00612	.01664

Table 29 Route 4 - Speed T-test

4.4.3 Trajectory

In the last route, VISSIM and the iBike behave in almost the same way. No limitations were found through this route as it was done in a car park with no traffic at the moment of the experiment. Turnings were the focal point in this route and differences can be appreciated in Figure 51. The picture shows how VISSIM simulation keeps the same distance from the curb and in this seed goes always in the middle of the lane. In this route the wide lane allowed the cyclist to move freely and it can be noticed that the iBike seem to change its distance from the curb before and after a turning which was already observed in the first route.

Figure 51 Route 4 – Reconstructed trajectories. Map created with GPS Visualizer

4.5 Speed

After analysing datasets from each route, all datasets were merged to analyse overall speed and acceleration distributions. From Table 30 a wider speed range in iBike can be appreciated with both datasets having a minimum value close to the zero but with a higher maximum value in the iBike 27.87 km/h against 21.24 km/h in VISSIM. From 5th percentiles, it can be noticed that even when both datasets have a similar minimum value, the VISSIM data does not have as many low-speed observations as the iBike, 13.43 km/h and 5.82 km/h respectively. Average speed is higher in VISSIM, as it was in all routes, with 16.26 km/h and 12.32 km/h in iBike. Contrary, the standard deviation is higher in iBike than in VISSIM, 3.55 km/h and 1.99 km/h.

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	181859	64716
Mean		12.3215	16.2606
Std. Deviation		3.54599	1.99190
Variance		12.574	3.968
Range		27.83	21.23
Minimum		.04	.01
Maximum		27.87	21.24
Percentiles	5	5.8200	13.4300
	25	10.4900	15.2800
	50	12.5500	16.2000
	75	14.5200	17.6300
	95	17.7200	18.8600

Table 30 Speed descriptive statistics

In Figure 52 speed data sets distribution is illustrated. It can be noticed that iBike observations are better distributed while in VISSIM there are two peaks where most data is concentrated around 15 km/h and 18 km/h. It also shows how iBike range is wider and how almost no VISSIM's observations are below 11 km/h. VISSIM speed distribution appears to be different from iBike's distribution with faster speeds and smaller variation. In order to verify this, a t-test was done.

Figure 52 Speed distribution iBike/VISSIM

The central limit theorem was applied due to the large sample size and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, consequently, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Afterwards, the test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 31 below.

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Speed	Equal variances assumed	16473.112	.000	-267.954	246573	.000	-3.93914	.01470	-3.96795	-3.91032
	Equal variances not assumed			-344.888	201700.149	.000	-3.93914	.01142	-3.96152	-3.91675

Table 31 Speed T-test

In order to confirm the t-test results, a non-parametric test was conducted. A Mann-Whitney U-test was done to check whether the population median supported the previous conclusion which stated that the two populations were not the same. The test found significant evidence that the median speeds were not equal. Thus, even if the normality assumption does not hold, the conclusion that distributions are not the same prevails. The results and significance level are shown in Table 32.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Speed is the same across categories of iBikeVISSIM.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

Table 32 Speed U-Test

4.6 Acceleration

Acceleration distributions in 3 of the 4 routes were found different. And even in the only route that was found equal, the distribution graph was not consistent with the result (see Figure 41). This possible is a result of the test used to compare them as the T-test focus on the means, which are expected to be close to zero, instead of the variance, in fact, the Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level. Through the different routes it was noticed that acceleration through time in VISSIM tend to be constant in relatively long periods and this was not observed in the iBike datasets.

Statistics

		iBike	VISSIM
N	Valid	180513	65807
Mean		.0103	.0022
Std. Deviation		.35281	.28373
Variance		.124	.081
Minimum		-2.84	-5.47
Maximum		4.86	3.40
Percentiles	5	-.5500	-.2800
	25	-.1900	-.0700
	50	.0000	.0000
	75	.2100	.0000
	95	.5800	.3200

Table 33 Acceleration descriptive statistics

The whole datasets from the four routes were compared and results are shown in Table 33 and Figure 53. Acceleration mean and standard deviation are close to zero in both cases as expected but are little higher in the iBike. Maximum and minimum values are greater than in literature review however this is mainly outliers as it can be appreciated when comparing them with the 5th and 95th percentiles. Additionally, from percentiles, symmetric distribution can be expected and in the chart below it can be better appreciated. Also, from the graph, a more spread distribution in the iBike’s dataset can be observed. In addition, a great

percentage of VISSIM's observations are concentrated around zero which does not happen in the iBike and should be reviewed.

Figure 53 Acceleration distribution iBike/VISSIM

The central limit theorem was applied due to the large sample size and thus the two datasets were assumed to be normally distributed. Levene's test demonstrated that the variances of the two datasets were significantly different at 5% significance level, consequently, Independent Samples T-Test without equal variances assumption were conducted to compare the average speeds between iBike and VISSIM. Afterwards, the test found significant evidence that the average speeds were not equal. The significance level of both the Levene's test and the Independent Sample T-Test can be found in Table 34 below.

		Independent Samples Test					t-test for Equality of Means		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Acceleration	Equal variances assumed	14245.950	.000	5.294	246318	.000	.00809	.00153	.00510	.01109
	Equal variances not assumed			5.853	144198.334	.000	.00809	.00138	.00538	.01081

Table 34 Acceleration T-test

Chapter 4: Results and Analysis

In order to confirm the t-test results, a non-parametric test was conducted. A Mann-Whitney U-test was done to check whether the population median supported the previous conclusion which stated that the two populations were not the same. The test found significant evidence that the median speeds were not equal. Thus, even if the normality assumption does not hold, the conclusion that distributions are not the same prevails. The results and significance level are shown in Table 35.

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Acceleration is the same across categories of iBikeVISSIM.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

Table 35 Acceleration U-test

Chapter 5: Discussion and conclusions

Cycling and walking are sustainable modes of transport which are intended to be increased in the upcoming years. Some benefits of cycling were mentioned highlighting the health benefits to the users. In addition, the UK investment strategy which aims to improve and encourage cycling in order to reduce traffic congestion and pollution was mentioned. Greater cycling infrastructure is proposed, aiming to deliver safer, better integrated and more attractive routes. For this to be realised, detailed planning is required, and traffic simulation software is a key available tool.

Traffic simulation software categories were specified. For cycling infrastructure planning a microsimulation was stated to be the best to use. Most used microsimulation software in the UK was mentioned. PTV VISSIM software, which is recommended by TfL streets traffic directorate, was addressed. VISSIM cyclist model and the Copenhagen study was reviewed.

COWI, a consulting group, was hired by the Copenhagen government to calibrate the VISSIM cyclist model. Collected GPS and video data were used to calibrate ten cyclist behaviour parameters with PTV group help. However, its application in the UK had not been assessed. Therefore, the aim of this research was to investigate the realism of the VISSIM cyclist model in the UK context. In order to do it, an instrumented bike was used to collect cyclist trajectory data to then compare it with VISSIM software.

Controlled scenarios with different road characteristics were selected and modelled using VISSIM software. Next, volunteers were asked to ride the iBike through the four defined routes around Highfield campus. Using video recorded from the iBike, the VISSIM models were calibrated in order to do them as real as possible. Then, from the iBike, speed, acceleration and trajectory coordinates were extracted. Same data was extracted from VISSIM software to then compare them.

5.1 Research contributions

This research found significant evidence that average speed from iBike's collected data and VISSIM are not the same and therefore, needs to be recalibrated. Additionally, differences in accelerations through time were found. Mainly the VISSIM constant accelerations in relatively long periods, which were not observed in the real measurements taken using the iBike. Moreover, change in distance from the curb before and after a turn was observed in the recorded videos and the reconstructed trajectory. The differences found in this research can be used as a first step to calibrate the VISSIM cyclist model for the UK practice.

5.2 Limitations

Although this research was mainly based on COWI's project (2013) it did not assess the ten parameters which they stated are important for cycling simulation. This was chiefly for safety reasons of the volunteers involved but also because of the system used to collect data i.e. following parameters could not be measured with the only iBike available. Therefore, only the basic parameters were able to be studied. The results found speed and acceleration distributions in the UK different from the simulated in VISSIM, which were calibrated using Copenhagen data. However, this can be a result of other factors listed below.

- The iBike was developed from a Santander bike which was designed to be durable. As a result, iBike's weight is heavier than a usual bicycle and this might have influenced the speed and acceleration.
- The number of volunteers and its variety was too small compared to the sample used in Copenhagen's project.
- Free flow conditions were looked at, but a traffic light interfered with route one. Also, pedestrians and cars caused volunteers to reduce their speed as they were obstructing the routes. Consequently, the speed went close to 0 km/h in some points of the experiment which was not the case in Copenhagen's experiment (see Table 2)
- All experiment was run around Highfield campus in Southampton city which might not be representative of the UK population.
- Volunteers followed a bike which indicated them where to go. This could influence the participant's cycling behaviour in addition to their speed and acceleration.
- VISSIM model was done with measurements obtained from google earth and Bing maps which might not be accurate.

Similarly, some limitations of the software to faithfully simulate the field experiment were mentioned. However, these limitations could have been corrected using existing software tools if more experience with the software was acquired. Namely, the reduced time to learn and use the software could lead to a lower simulation quality. Likewise, a greater sample could have obtained if more time was available. Finally, iBike's use was subject to Dr Miah availability which also limited data obtention.

5.3 Future work

This research had some limitations which can be addressed in future works. Suggestions are listed below.

- Only the cycling micro-simulation basic parameters were analysed. Therefore, a future work assessing parameters regarding bicycle paths and intersections is needed.
- Data collection was limited to a relatively small area in Southampton. Future works can collect data from more locations that better represent the UK population.

Chapter 5: Discussion and conclusions

- Increase the number of volunteers used to collect data will help to get more diverse results.
- Use the speed and acceleration distributions obtained from this research to calibrate the VISSIM's cyclist model to then be used in the UK.
- Study the cyclist behaviour focusing on the change in distance from the curb before and after a turn.

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Appendix

Timestamp	INS_Latitu	INS_Longi	INS_Elevat	INS_Roll	INS_Pitch	INS_Yaw	INS_Pulse	INS_Distar	INS_Speed	INS_Raw	INS_Raw	INS_Raw	INS_Raw	INS_gForc	iBike_S_Ac	iBike_S_Ac	iBike_S_Ac	iBike_S_G	iBike_S_G	iBike_S_G	iBike_Acc	iBike_Acc	iBike_Acc	iBike_Gyrc	iBike_Gyrc	iBike_Gyrc	iBike_Mag	iBike_Mag	iBike_Mag	iBike_A2K	iBike_UCT	iBike_UCP	iBike_Pulsi	iBike_Pulsi	iBike_Mari	iBike_Gyro
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41924	-9.32304	-7.32688	42.44354	183	16.24472	0	-1.68907	1.737341	-9.54333	1.013157	62	-14	19	1	-31	-191	13	-2	58	85	-167	-456	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	14	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41924	-9.32304	-7.32688	42.44354	183	16.24472	0	-1.68907	1.737341	-9.54333	1.013157	61	-13	21	72	-3	-347	14	0	56	71	-92	-708	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	34	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.42043	-9.19149	-7.32979	42.40676	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.996643	61	-13	22	60	-42	-347	11	1	59	-162	325	-743	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.42043	-9.19149	-7.32979	42.40676	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.996643	60	-12	23	23	12	-420	11	2	58	198	304	-454	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.42043	-9.19149	-7.32979	42.40676	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.996643	60	-10	22	169	22	-390	9	2	58	212	534	-186	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.42043	-9.19149	-7.32979	42.40676	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.996643	61	-9	22	143	18	-349	7	3	57	187	547	245	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.42043	-9.19149	-7.32979	42.40676	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.996643	61	-8	21	33	-23	-200	5	2	57	151	1012	440	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41301	-9.09229	-7.34853	42.35991	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.999331	61	-8	20	103	-13	-190	6	5	58	205	790	657	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41301	-9.09229	-7.34853	42.35991	183	16.24472	0	-1.7626	1.383704	-9.42179	0.999331	62	-9	19	143	-14	-117	4	5	58	118	724	840	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	23	
09:57.7	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41257	-9.03919	-7.3619	42.31959	183	16.24472	0	-1.26767	0.990029	-9.52924	0.993362	62	-9	17	34	-4	-32	6	5	59	25	546	825	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:57.8	50.93818	-1.39403	91.41257	-9.03919	-7.3619	42.31959	183	16.24472	0	-1.26767	0.990029	-9.52924	0.993362	60	-9	16	-6	-12	-31	8	4	59	-55	796	664	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.8	50.93818	-1.39403	91.40546	-9.01605	-7.37829	42.28109	183	16.24472	0	-0.93748	1.271447	-9.60951	1.00053	65	-12	18	-39	-36	45	8	-2	60	-93	469	328	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:57.8	50.93818	-1.39403	91.40546	-9.01605	-7.37829	42.28109	183	16.24472	0	-0.93748	1.271447	-9.60951	1.00053	63	-10	17	36	-30	-129	12	2	63	-24	-679	52	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	23	
09:57.8	50.93818	-1.39403	91.40611	-9.00831	-7.38755	42.25186	183	16.24472	0	-0.93748	1.271447	-9.60951	1.040538	60	-12	17	31	-29	-119	9	5	58	105	-77	-325	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:57.8	50.93818	-1.39403	91.40607	-8.97356	-7.3695	42.23572	183	16.24472	0	-0.89853	1.329658	-9.37605	0.977507	56	-5	18	13	1	-64	8	6	56	-23	-43	-191	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.9	50.93818	-1.39403	91.40607	-8.97356	-7.3695	42.23572	183	16.24472	0	-0.89853	1.329658	-9.37605	0.977507	71	-9	22	-3	-45	76	12	4	60	50	72	112	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:57.9	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39896	-8.98531	-7.38396	42.23249	183	16.24472	0	-0.89853	1.329658	-9.37605	0.98837	63	-5	20	125	-115	175	7	3	62	-2	-10	239	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:57.9	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39896	-8.98531	-7.38396	42.23249	183	16.24472	0	-1.16366	0.597234	-9.53072	0.98837	64	-5	18	-137	160	9	8	57	83	71	564	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	0	22	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39996	-9.00923	-7.35713	42.16323	183	16.24472	0	-1.16366	0.597234	-9.53072	0.990237	60	-17	19	10	85	254	9	22	61	84	237	824	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39996	-9.00923	-7.35713	42.16323	183	16.24472	0	-1.16366	0.597234	-9.53072	0.990237	64	-11	21	-144	18	468	7	2	54	-13	218	1450	388	287	-101	89	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39253	-9.14671	-7.38614	42.13975	183	16.24472	0	-1.14221	0.764612	-9.45851	0.982132	63	-5	20	-166	-85	352	11	0	57	83	225	1529	388	287	-101	89	24816	44721	0	0	0	23	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39291	-9.13107	-7.38234	42.12806	183	16.24472	0	-1.14221	0.764612	-9.45851	1.006301	57	-6	20	-38	-115	537	6	-3	63	-50	128	1145	388	287	-101	88	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39291	-9.13107	-7.38234	42.12806	183	16.24472	0	-1.54693	0.383632	-9.6611	1.006301	63	-16	19	-107	-44	644	6	0	58	-171	-174	632	388	287	-101	88	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.0	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39298	-9.51312	-7.41223	42.05709	183	16.24472	0	-1.54693	0.383632	-9.6611	1.016673	62	-13	18	-92	-97	566	4	7	58	-159	-350	410	388	287	-101	88	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.1	50.93818	-1.39403	91.39298	-9.51312	-7.41223	42.05709	183	16.24472	0	-1.47732	2.10452	-9.54238	1.016673	62	-12	18	-179	-49	447	12	3	57	-253	-347	337	388	287	-101	88	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.1	50.93818	-1.39403	91.38493	-9.68479	-7.41903	42.08257	183	16.24472	0	-1.47732	2.10452	-9.54238	1.031544	64	-14	20	-194	-75	227	12	-12	59	-138	-322	-677	388	287	-101	88	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.1	50.93818	-1.39403	91.38493	-9.68479	-7.41903	42.08257	183	16.24472	0	-1.13198	2.337533	-9.69165	1.031544	63	-15	20	-8	-93	163	7	-7	64	-325	-786	-1493	388	287	-101	89	24816	44721	0	0	0	22	
09:58.1	50.93818	-1.39403	91.38584	-9.76857	-7.41309	42.05898	183	16.24472	0	-1.28985	2.092895	-9.81603	1.040341	60	-13	19	-165	-20	151	5	6	56	-461	-1012	-1852	388	287	-101	89	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:58.2	50.93818	-1.39403	91.37846	-9.84252	-7.41023	42.1049	183	16.24472	0	-1.28985	2.092895	-9.81603	0.9963	62	-10	18	-287	43	145	3	7	56	-482	-985	-1772	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	23	
09:58.2	50.93818	-1.39403	91.37846	-9.84252	-7.41023	42.1049	183	16.24472	0	-1.17642	2.156371	-9.37047	0.9963	63	-8	20	-299	-43	102	11	1	58	-417	-1109	-1641	388	287	-101	90	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:58.2	50.93818	-1.39403	91.37846	-9.84252	-7.41023	42.1049	183	16.24472	0	-1.17642	2.156371	-9.37047	0.9963	61	-9	19	-203	-37	259	12	2	60	-337	-975	-1597	388	287	-101	91	24816	44721	0	0	0	23	
09:58.2	50.93818	-1.39403	91.37804	-9.92581	-7.38945	42.15272	183	16.24472	0	-1.20211	0.584994	-9.78015	1.013861	60	-14	19	-34	-9	249	12	2	56	-448	-1032	-1741	388	287	-101	92	24816	44721	0	0	0	21	
09:58.2	50.93818	-1.39403	91.37804	-9.92581	-7.38945	42.15272	183	16.24472	0	-1.20211	0.584994</																									